

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

1 KG IRON VS 1 KG COTTON WOOL: THE OBJECTIVITY OF EXAMINATION TESTS

Berezhiani Malkhaz

Professor, PhD in Engineering Science

Georgian Technical University,

Faculty of Agrarian and Biosystems Engineering

17 Guramishvili Av. Tbilisi, 0192, Georgia

Abstract

The well-known school question-joke about weighing of a kilogram of iron and a kilogram of cotton wool is considered. The correct answer takes into account the influence of Archimedean force, the Earth's magnetic field, the gravity and the centrifugal force caused by Earth rotation. Rated assessments of these factors under some external conditions are given. On the example of this task are illustrated the possible problems of evaluating real knowledge of the student, based on the results of closed type examination tests.

Keywords: mass, weight, density, Archimedean force, magnetic field, gravity, centrifugal force, examination tests.

Trap question: "What is heavier – a kilogram of iron or a kilogram of cotton wool?" provokes an intuitive wrong answer about the greater weight of iron, but the "correct" answer that both are equally heavy does not take into account the difference between the concepts of "kilogram" and "heavy". The kilogram is a unit of mass, and heaviness represents the force exerted by a body on a support, in particular on a scale platform. Semantically, the word "heaviness" generally is a definition of the force required to lift an object from a surface. When weighing an object under normal earthly conditions, several factors influence the weighing results:

- 1) Archimedean force, which depends on the volume of the body and the specific gravity of air.
- 2) The Earth's magnetic field affects ferromagnetic materials.
- 3) The force of gravity of Earth itself depends on the distance of the center of mass of the body; the distance is greater for a larger object.

4) The centrifugal force caused by the rotation of Earth also depends on the distance of the center of mass of the body.

Let's imagine a thought experiment of the process of weighing bodies with a mass of 1 kg made of iron and cotton wool in the natural conditions of the earth, taking quite common simplifications:

- the bodies are cubic in shape;
- bodies are located on same horizontal surface at the level of the Earth's radius;
- we assume that the axis of rotation of Earth - the geographic pole coincides with the magnetic pole.

In Fig. 1. A drawing of the influence of various forces on a body lying on the earth's surface is presented. Of course, to ensure clarity, the scales of geometry and vectors of physical quantities are not observed.

Pic. 1. Drawing to represent the influence of various forces on weight

The following discussions and calculations do not exceed the science knowledge requirements for student of a technical/engineering college. The numerical values of various physical quantities needed for calculations are easily found on the Internet, for this reason all references are given in the form of quick links to Internet resources.

Below are given the initial data and some accepted assumptions for the calculations.

Mass of bodies $m=1$ kg.

Air density under normal conditions: temperature $T=273.15$ K and atmospheric pressure $P=760$ mm Hg = 101325 Pa is equal to [1] $\rho_{A0} = 1.293$ kg/m³. Under other conditions:

$$\rho_A = \rho_{A0} \frac{273.15 \cdot P}{T \cdot 101235} \quad (1)$$

Density of iron and cotton wool respectively [2]: $\rho_{Fe} = 7874$ kg/m³, $\rho_{Cot} = 30$ kg/m³. Based on the hygroscopicity of cotton wool, we assume that the cubic packing of cotton wool is airtight sealed, the net mass is taken into account and the density refers to the entire porous volume.

Mean, polar and equatorial radius of the earth respectively [3]: $R_M = 6371$ km = 6 371 000 m, $R_P = 6357$ km = 6 357 000 m, $R_E = 6378$ km = 6 378 000 m.

Average value of acceleration due to gravity $g = 9.807$ m/s².

Angular frequency of earth rotation:

$$\varpi = \frac{2\pi}{24 \cdot 3600} = 7.27 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$$

The average strength of the earth's magnetic field is accepted [4] $H = 40$ A/m.

Magnetic susceptibility of iron for weak field [5] $\kappa = 1100$.

For calculations, the force value for 1 A/m is used [6] $f_A = 2 \cdot 10^{-7}$ N [6].

We accept middle geographic latitude $\alpha = 45^\circ$, magnetic inclination β is simplified to equate to geo-

graphic latitude $\beta = \alpha$, but generally $\beta > \alpha$, for example for Moscow: $\alpha = 55^\circ$, $\beta = 70^\circ$; for Odessa: $\alpha = 46^\circ$, $\beta = 60^\circ$ [7,8,9].

$$\text{Body volume calculated as: } V = \frac{m}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

Cube edge size $a = \sqrt[3]{V}$, respectively:
 $a_{Fe} = 0.050$ m, $a_{Cot} = 0.322$ m.

$$\text{Center of mass height } h = \frac{a}{2}, \text{ respectively}$$

$$\Delta h = \frac{a_{Cot} - a_{Fe}}{2} = 0.136 \text{ m.}$$

The difference between the corresponding forces is represented by a positive value $\Delta F = F_{Fe} - F_{Cot}$. As $\Delta h \ll R$, for distance dependent forces finite differences ΔF , Δh (same ΔR) are assumed as differentials $dF = F' dr$. The g change with the local radius R of the earth is taken into account.

Archimedean force difference calculated:

$$\Delta F_A = \rho_A (V_{Cot} - V_{Fe}) g \frac{R_M^2}{R^2} \quad (3)$$

Magnetic force affects only ferromagnetic iron, the radial (local vertical) component of the force vector calculated:

$$\Delta F_{mR} = F_{mRFe} = \kappa H^2 f_A a_{Fe}^2 \sin(\beta) \quad (4)$$

Gravitational force difference calculated:

$$\Delta F_G = mg \frac{R_M^2}{R^2} \cdot \frac{2\Delta h}{R} \quad (5)$$

The radial component of centrifugal force vector difference calculated:

$$\Delta F_{CR} = m\varpi^2 \Delta h \cos^2(\alpha) \quad (6)$$

Calculation results are given in table 1. For clarity, the values are presented in common technical units kgf.

Table 1.

Calculated difference in weighing of 1 kg iron and cotton wool

Values	Middle latitude	Polar region	Equatorial region
Earth radius R, km	6371	6357	6378
Temperature T, K	273.15	250	303
Latitude (magnetic) $\alpha(\beta)$, °	45	90	0
Archimedean force ΔF_A , kgf	$4.29 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$4.71 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.38 \cdot 10^{-2}$
Magnetic force ΔF_m , kgf	$6.41 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$9.07 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0
Gravity force ΔF_G , kgf	$4.26 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$4.29 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$4.25 \cdot 10^{-8}$
Centrifugal force ΔF_C , kgf	$3.66 \cdot 10^{-11}$	0	$7.32 \cdot 10^{-11}$

It follows that for middle latitude and normal conditions in order: Archimedes force - magnetic force - gravitational force - centrifugal force, each next value decreases by about 1000 times. Calculations were carried out for extreme latitudes of the earth as well.

From these calculations it is clear that the influence of the last two factors is less than the deviation (up to 100 μ g) between the control samples of the kilogram

mass standard [10]. The theoretical influence of centrifugal force on the weighing difference is less than the accuracy of the modern unit of mass according to the Planck constant, which is defined to the 9th digit [11], although the absolute magnitude of the influence on earth's gravity is significant to take into account the direction and location of spacecraft launches.

If we imagine that a student on an exam must answer such a "simple" question in the form of a closed

test without additional clarification, both the student and the examiner will encounter difficulty, but in the case of an open question, a competent student could briefly state a conceptually correct idea. The same task in the form of homework or a project can easily be solved using quantitative assessments, as presented above.

The real problem of weighing a person weighing 100 kg (assumed: $Z_{Man}=1.85$ m, $h=0.55Z$; $\rho_{Man}=1000$ kg/m³) using scales, precisely calibrated by 5 pieces of iron weights of 20 kg each ($a_{Fe} = 0.136$ m), is also considered. During the calibration process, the weights are located parallel to the scale platform. The calculation results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2.

Calculated error in determining the mass of a 100 kg person by weighing

Values	Middle latitude	Polar region	Equatorial region
Archimedean force ΔF_A , kgf	$1.13 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.24 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.02 \cdot 10^{-1}$
Magnetic force ΔF_m , kgf	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.34 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0
Gravity force ΔF_G , kgf	$2.98 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.00 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$2.97 \cdot 10^{-5}$
Centrifugal force ΔF_C , kgf	$2.56 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0	$5.12 \cdot 10^{-8}$

Conclusions. Conceptually strong answer takes into account the influence of Archimedean force, the Earth's magnetic field, the gravity and the centrifugal force caused by Earth rotation. The influence of the Archimedean force and magnetic field factors on weighing are noticeable, but not the difference in gravitational forces and, even less so, the centrifugal forces.

References

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